

Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Skills and Digital Proficiency of Teachers

Ailyn M. Latonio

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the extent of information and communication technology skills of TLE Teachers and the extent of digital proficiency of Teachers in Cluster 1 Secondary School of Davao City. In this study, quantitative research design using descriptive correlational was used in collecting and analyzing the data obtained from all the respondents. One hundred twenty (120) teachers of the Cluster 1 Schools of Davao City teaching TLE were randomly selected through simple random sample technique to answer the designed questionnaire. Using mean, Pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of information and communication technology skills of TLE Teachers and the extent of digital proficiency of teachers was extensive. Evidently, it was found out that all of the indicators were significantly related to digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE. Moreover, result showed the significance on the influence of ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE and revealed that ICT skills has a significant influence in the digital proficiency of teachers teaching TLE obtaining an R-value of 0.788 and R² of 0.620 with an F value of 192.891 and a p-value of 0.000. Based on the statistical result it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE. Thus, teachers are open towards the use of ICT in teaching, not being resistant and feels comfortable in learning new things.

KEY WORDS

1. teachers' information and communications technology skills 2. digital proficiency 3. TLE Teachers

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1. Introduction

Information technologies is a tool for improving quality education. A mechanism at the school education level that could provide a way to rethink and redesign the educational systems and processes, that will lead to quality education for all. Teachers are less confident using ICT in promoting the development of more complex teaching and learning processes, such as strategies of analysis, communication, evaluation and organization. Teachers' today, should possess ICT skills and improve effective teaching strategies for practical application in the classroom. It is imperative that teachers acquire technology skills for navigating the internet and take advantage on the enormous amount of available information in the web. The role of teachers is important in contributing the growth of the use of ICT in the classroom. Hence, it is important

for teachers to become computer literate, and be prepared to use information technology in schools. Being prepared to adopt and use technology and knowing how that technology can support student learning must become integral skills in every teacher's professional range. In South Africa, the use of information and communication technologies in teaching and learning is useful to the recent educational innovations. Information and Communication Technologies include but are not limited to electronic machine or devices used to help the teacher achieve the set goals and objectives in teaching and learning process. Instructional devices help teachers to communicate effectively to the students in a unique way of understanding that facilitates teaching and learning (Ojo Adu, 2018). According to Mdlongwa (2012), ICT is a global network in which ideas are exchanged, or information and knowledge is shared, through devices such as cell phones or computers, used to connect people. Also, the Department of Education of South Africa (2003) stated in the Draft White Paper on E-Education that Information and Communication Technologies could be described as the convergence of information technology and communication technology. It was further stated, that ICTs are the combination of networks, hardware, and software as well as the means of communication, collaboration, and engagement that enable the processing, management, and exchange of data, information, and knowledge. In the study of Ovic (2017) in Saudi Arabia Universities, the 21st century learning and education is important if not crucial that technology is taking place. It has led to improve teaching and learning processes, both inside and outside the classroom. One of its advantages is that it allows students and teachers to communicate outside the classroom and utilize new techniques and skills. The adoption of ICT in teaching has undoubtedly improved learning and teaching processes. Meanwhile, there are some factors hindering the successful implementation. His study concluded that lack of time, lack of training and lack of institutional support were the major factors influencing faculty members' decision to adopt and utilize technology in teaching practice. The provision of sufficient and practical training and institutional support for academic staff should be considered as essential to the successful implementation of technology in education by reducing academic staffs' workload to allow them to have more time to use E-learning tools. In the study of Abdelhak (2015) in Guelma University in Algeria, the effective integration of new technologies into the teaching and learning process is much more challenging than providing computers and securing classroom connection to the internet. It is associated with a shift from a teacher-expert to a student-centered approach of teaching and learning. Moreover, finding the appropriate mode of integrating technology into classroom practices is also one of the impediments that twenty-first century teachers will face. In developed nations, there is a shift from a teacher-centered to a student-centered setting, where teachers become collaborators instead of dispensers of knowledge; and where students become actively involved in their own education instead of passively receiving learning. To improve the pedagogical innovation, governments around the world placed an intensive effort into teachers' acceptance and the actual use of technology for instruction, yet there is limited literature about the conceptual framework of teachers accepting the use of it for instruction typically in the Asia-Pacific region. Teachers' effective practice of technology-based instruction under a mandatory context in the Philippines based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model. Through a survey conducted secondary school teachers in the Philippines, revealed that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and education policy have significant effects on teachers' behavioral intention to use technology

in the classroom, thus, teachers' habit and facilitating conditions have positive effects on the actual use of technology for instruction. The study then recommends a series of actions to improve research and policy on teachers' use of technology-based instruction (Lee, 2020). In the study of Dela Rosa, (2017), in developing ways on how to better deliver instruction has been regarded as beneficial in education. Information and Communication Technology is playing significant role. Hence, Bonifacio (2013) revealed that in the adoption of the fast advancing technological developments, the teachers must be provided with trainings and workshops for the integration of technology in the learning curricula. This is very important not only for the quality education that will be afforded to the students but also for the internal development of the Department of Education as an organization in itself. Mariano (2014) stated that the Philippine government has been committed to bring the educational system into a modernized status particularly on basic education. The country's effort to make each and every student at par with other students of neighboring developed countries. Along with this effort are the continuous curricular changes and amendments, reorientation, teacher training and investment in school facilities and infrastructures, one of which is geared towards the vision of equipping each public school with the modern computer and other instructional materials. The capability to utilize and produce information and to transform it into knowledge and vast array of goods and services is deemed essential to social development and growth of the economy. He further said that teachers, being the immediate medium of transferring knowledge and information to students, for in their hands depend the attainment of the Philippine education system's vision on the modernization of Basic Education. Challenged by new and innovative approaches, it may be painful to some teachers to lost grip from traditional teaching prac-

tices and strategies. On the other way, it may bring awareness and confidence to other teachers who tend to open their minds and hearts in embracing the demands of the advancing technology trends particularly on the attainment of quality education through innovative instruction. In the study of Chavez, Hernandez, Aparcana, Joaquin, Osore, Alcoser and Lozano (2020) revealed that the integration of ICT and digital skills in times of the pandemic COVID-19, as they allow students to learn and master technological tools making them compatible with virtual education. It was also showed that compatibility contributes to the adoption and integration of digital technology in teaching and learning, the emphasis lies on the alignment between the characteristics of technology and the characteristics of the task. Hence, technological innovations would be adopted as long as they fit the current situation and the costs are lower. At present, despite the advancement of technology, teachers still have difficulty in the use of ICT in teaching yet teachers are expected to select, develop, organize and use appropriate teaching and learning resources including technology-based to address learning goals. Teachers find the use of computers as cumbersome and time consuming specially in the preparation of materials and the setting up of the computer and projector make them reluctant to use the technology. The dilemma of teachers raises concerns on their willingness to learn the use the computers in teaching and learning, professional training and development in the utilization of computers. Few research and study in the field of ICT integration in the practical application in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education. Moreover, teachers are encouraged to find adequate time to develop new skills and explore the integration of digital technology integration into their existing teaching practices. Teachers facilitate learning and embrace it in the educative process through meaningful learning environment. Moreover, it remains a challenging task

on the part of the teachers due to lack of trainings, lack of confidence and competence, lack of technical support and lack of accessibility to resources.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this particular investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study will use quantitative research design using descriptive correlational in gathering data. In this research, quantitative methodology will be used to collect and analyze the data obtained from all the respondents. Descriptive research is a type of research that describes a population, situation, or phenomenon that is being studied. It focuses on answering the how, what, when, and where questions of a research problem, rather than the why. According Tanzeh (2011) Quantitative research is basically uses deductive-inductive approach, meaning that departs from a theoretical framework, the notion of experts, based on his experience and understanding of the researchers then developed into the problems and their solutions. Research design in this approach is specific and detailed. The resulting data is numeric data. Further, Grove, Burns and Gray (2013) specified that descriptive quantitative design maybe used to develop theory, identify problems with current practice, justify current practice, make judgements or determine what others in similar situations are doing.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in the Cluster 1 Schools of the Division of Davao City, comprising of seven schools. The respondents were teachers of the Cluster 1 Secondary Schools teaching Technology and Livelihood Education subjects. The researchers used random sampling method as a technique in selecting the respondents to answer the questionnaire. This type of technique was used when all individuals in a population have an equal chance of being selected. One

hundred twenty (120) teachers of the Cluster 1 Schools of Davao City teaching TLE were randomly selected through computer generated simple random samples to answer the designed questionnaire. Crossman, A. (2020), simple random sampling is the most basic and common type of sampling method used in quantitative social science research and in scientific research generally. This means that it guarantees that the sample chosen is representative of the population and that the sample is selected in an unbiased way. In turn, the statistical conclusions drawn from the analysis of the sample will be valid. There are multiple ways of creating a simple random sample. These include the lottery method, using a random number table, using a computer, and sampling with or without replacement. Ernvall and Nevalainen's (1982) concluded that for random sampling, implementation of the Random Draw Method using a computer-generated draw is most efficient if the population size (N) is known.

2.3. Research Instrument—The researcher used a modified and adopted questionnaire from International Journal of Research in Education and Science and from the Center for the Study of Learning and Performance. This questionnaire was validated by experts in the field of research and education. The comments and suggestions of the validators was incorporated in the final output of the modified questionnaire. Sections on the questionnaire were designed specifically to answer the statement of the problem with regard to the Teachers Information and Communications Technology Skills and Digital

Proficiency. To ensure the reliability of questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted in one of the schools of the Division of Davao City and calculating the value of Cronbach alpha obtaining a scale value of all variables as 0.903 and showed a very good internal consistency. This study has one set of questionnaires utilized and consist of three parts. Part I were the extent of information and communications technology skills of the TLE Teachers in terms of: computer Literacy, proficiency, professional views on computer technology and experience with computer technologies. While Part II are the extent of digital proficiency of TLE teachers in terms of teachers' perception of ICT integration

in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning. Part III are the teacher's proficiency and ability in the classroom using the secondary data which is the Teachers Classroom Observation Tool (COT) of SY 2020-2021.

The extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers were based on the following Five-point likert rating scale.

Meanwhile, to measure the teacher's proficiency and ability in the classroom, the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) of SY 2020-2021 were used based on the following scale.

Range and Interpretation of Information and Communication Technology Skills of TLE Teachers

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	This means that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers is very much evident.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	This means that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers is relatively evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	This means that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers is often felt evident.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	This means that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers is not so much evident.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	This means that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the TLE Teachers is not evident.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—

Range and Interpretation of Digital Proficiency of TLE Teachers in the Classroom

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very Extensive	This means that the extent of digital proficiency of TLE Teachers in the classroom is practiced all the time.
3.40–4.19	Extensive	This means that the extent of digital proficiency of TLE Teachers in the classroom is practiced most of the time.
2.60–3.39	Moderately Extensive	This means that the extent of digital proficiency of TLE Teachers in the classroom is practiced sometimes.
1.80–2.59	Less Extensive	This means that the extent of digital proficiency of TLE Teachers in the classroom is practiced rarely.
1.00–1.79	Not Extensive	This means that the extent of digital proficiency of TLE Teachers in the classroom is never practiced.

To facilitate an efficient procedure, the researcher wrote a request letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent, asking permission therein to conduct survey among the secondary school TLE Teachers of Cluster 1. Upon approval by the Superintendent and upon the receipt of the indorsement letter, the researcher complied whatever instruction stipulated in the letter as afforded by the office and its intent therein. Then, the researcher wrote a letter to the Principal of the Cluster 1 Secondary Schools of Davao City and personally distributed the letter to the Principal/ head of the school requesting and informing them of the study prior to the floating of survey tools through google forms and retrieved the receiving copy of the letter automatically. After the approval of the School Principal, the respon-

dents were given researcher-adopted and modified questionnaire through the use of google form. The researcher forwarded the said questionnaire through google link. The researcher retrieved the questionnaire in the internal storage device of the google forms. To follow the protocol ethics in research, the researcher sought voluntary participation in the study and the request letter were stipulated in the questionnaire addressed to the respondent- TLE teachers for their participation in providing the needed data for the study. The responses, upon retrieval from the google form were subjected for consolidation and analysis ready for interpretation. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis and interpretation. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis—*

Levels of Pedagogical Indicators

Level	Level Label	Level Description
3	Organizing	The teacher demonstrates a limited range of loosely-associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator.
4	Developing	The teacher demonstrates a range of associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator that sometimes are aligned with the learners' developmental needs.
5	Applying	The teacher demonstrates a range of associated pedagogical aspects of the indicator that usually are aligned with the learners' developmental needs.
6	Consolidating	The teacher uses well-connected pedagogical aspects of the indicator that consistently are aligned with student development and support students to be successful learners.
7	Integrating	The teacher uses well-connected pedagogical aspects of the indicator to create an environment that addresses individual and group learning goals.

The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in the study. Mean. This will be used to determine the level of information and communication and technology skills of the TLE Teachers in terms of: computer Literacy, proficiency, professional views on computer technology and experience with computer technologies and the level of teachers practices in teaching and practical application in terms of teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool will be used in determining the significant relationship between the level of information and communication and technology skills of the TLE Teachers and level of teachers practices in teaching and practical application in the classroom. Regression Analysis. This was utilized to determine the domains of ICT skills that significantly influence the digital proficiency of teachers teaching TLE.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter are the results of the data gathered. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged accordingly. The extent of information and communication technology skills of the Teachers in terms of professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency. The extent of digital proficiency of the teacher's in terms of

Teachers’ perception of ICT integration in teaching, Teachers’ effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning.

Extent of Teachers Information and Communication Technology Skills

Presented in table 1 shows the summary of the Extent of Teachers Information and Communication Technology Skills. The overall mean of the teachers’ information and communication technology skills obtain an overall mean of 4.12 which has a descriptive equivalent of exten-

sive which means that the extent of ICT skills for TLE teachers is relatively evident. It means that TLE Teachers’ information and communication technology skills is relatively evident with the professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency of the TLE Teachers.

Table 1. Summary Table on the Teachers’ Information and Communication Technology Skills

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Professional Views on Computer Technology	4.13	Extensive
2	Computer Literacy	4.23	Very Extensive
3	Computer Proficiency	3.99	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.12	Extensive

It can be gleaned from the table that professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency is relatively evident. This implies that teachers can utilize Information and Communication Technology in the teaching and learning process as evident that ICT skills is extensive. Thus, findings are in conjunction with the study of Ogundele and Etejere (2013) who found out that in order to increase efficiency and effectiveness in curriculum delivery and records keeping, teachers use computers in classroom teaching and learning processes. It expresses the view that electronic information systems allow teachers to acquire information on learning instruction materials through the use of Internet. This is also in consonance that teachers must have knowledge of the use of technology skills to level with the fast-changing computer-based technology. Teachers

must have the skills in different computer applications such but not limited to word processing skills, spreadsheet skills, database skills, electronic presentation skills, internet navigation skills, e-mail management skills, videos, file management, installing software to a device, troubleshooting, using information technology tools and the like (Catanaoan, 2017).

The Extent of Digital Proficiency of the Teacher’s Summary of the digital proficiency of the Teachers. Presented in table 2 shows the summary of the digital proficiency of the Teachers. The overall mean of the digital proficiency of the Teachers obtain an overall mean of 4.04 which has a descriptive equivalent of extensive which means that the digital proficiency of TLE Teachers is practiced most of the time. This means that digital proficiency of TLE Teachers is practiced most of the time with the teachers’

perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning.

Table 2. Summary Table on the Digital Proficiency of Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Teachers' Perception of ICT Integration in Teaching	4.17	Extensive
2	Teachers' Effectiveness on the Integration of ICT in the Classroom	4.14	Extensive
3	Factors in ICT Integration in Teaching and Learning	3.82	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.04	Extensive

The aforementioned results mean that the indicators, teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning is extensive. Thus, result showed that digital proficiency of the TLE Teachers in the classroom is practiced most of the time. Thus, teachers are open towards the use of ICT in teaching, not being resistant and feels comfortable in learning new things. This result is anchored in the study of Waiganjo (2021), stated that because of booming growth, usage of technology in today's world is propelling many teachers to integrate technology in the classroom. It was also stated that the methods of teaching and learning which uses technology to support enhancement and optimize the delivering of information is referred to as ICT in education. He further asserted that it can lead to better quality student learning and better teaching methods. Technology in education is simply incorporating teaching and learning methodologies and technology to have innovative lessons in the classroom. To integrate digital technologies into practice, teachers

need an ever-evolving understanding of which technologies exist and their functionalities (DeCoito and Richardson, 2018). The findings also supported by the study of Sabzian and Gilakjani (2013) which revealed that teachers training should not be limited to the use of computer technology but it should include the skills on how they can make use of computer technology in improving the quality and effectiveness of their instruction. Thus, training and assistance is essential in helping teachers to better integrate computer technology resources in their pedagogic practices. Furthermore, digitally literate individuals are able to search for online resources that could assist with troubleshooting and keying in the right questions in a search engine that would enable to retrieve responses in the form of text, images and videos that will assist with solving the problem. Updating of antivirus software to avoid spam and viruses, is also part of digital literacy learning (Ng, 2012).

Significance on the relationship between teachers' information communication technology (ICT) skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observa-

tion rating As shown in the table 3, were the results for the test of relationship between the variables of interest in this research. The overall r-value of 0.788 and p-value of 0.000 which is lower than the set alpha of 0.05 signifying rejection of the null hypothesis; therefore, there is a significant relationship between teachers' information communication technology (ICT)

skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating. The grand overall result also implies that there is a strong positive correlation in relationship between teachers' information communication technology (ICT) skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating.

Table 3: Significance on the Relationship Between Teachers' ICT Skills and Digital Proficiency Technology Skills of TLE Teachers' Classroom Observation Rating

Teachers' Skills	ICT	Teachers' Perception of ICT Integration in Teaching	Teachers' Effectiveness on the Integration of ICT in the Classroom	Factors in ICT Integration and Learning	Overall	Decision on Ho
Professional Views on Computer Technology		0.721	0.688	0.604	0.767	Reject
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
Computer Literacy		0.660	0.507	0.506	0.638	Reject
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
Computer Proficiency	Profi-	0.746	0.541	0.563	0.706	Reject
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
Overall					0.788	Reject
					0.000	

The individual obtained r-value for the teachers' ICT skills showed, Professional Views on Computer Technology with an r-value of 0.767 and a p-value of 0.000, Computer Literacy with an r-value of 0.638 and a p-value of 0.000, and Computer Proficiency with an r-value of 0.706 and a p-value of 0.000. This

also means that these indicators significantly related to digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating. Conspicuously, it was found that all of the indicators, teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in

ICT integration in teaching and learning were significantly related to digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating. Thus, the results indicate that when digital communication is more used, it is more likely also its integration in the classroom. Theoretically, digital competence are sets of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that enables individual to achieve goals using digital technologies in various life contexts (Ferrari, Punie, Redecker, 2012). Technological change challenges teaching professionals at two levels: first, to develop their own digital competences, and second, to develop instructional activities that equip all students with the competences needed to succeed in the digitalized world. For example, alongside supporting traditional literacy skills, teachers have to support literacy skills in digital settings (Harteis, 2019). Moreover, in the study of Waiganjo (2021), stated that because of booming growth, usage of technology in today's world is propelling many teachers to integrate technology in the classrooms. Furthermore, in the study conducted by Beardsley, Albo, Aragon and Leo (2020) revealed that teachers believe their proficiency in using digital technologies for teaching has improved. Teacher confidence in using ICT for preparing lessons, class teaching, assessing and providing feedback, and for communicating with students and families has increased along with teacher motivation to improve their ICT skills and use digital technologies for teaching. Most of the teacher lack the technological proficiency needed to use in the classroom, making them unable to bring these technologies into the classroom and leading to many standing unused in the classroom. Teachers need not only to learn how to use technol-

The regression analysis agreed statistically that there is a significant influence of the ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE. This implies that when all the in-

ogy at a basic level but also to learn how to integrate that technology into the classroom. Hence, teachers must be taught how their acquired skills can be used to integrate technology into the classroom to provide multifaceted engagement for their students (Mundy, Kupczynski Kee, 2012). Meanwhile, the findings of the present study is consistent with the results of the previous studies in terms of significant relationship.

Significance on the Influence of ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE.

Presented in Table 4 are the results of regression analysis, which showed the significance on the influence of ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE. Results revealed that the ICT skills has a significant influence in the digital proficiency of teachers teaching TLE obtaining an R-value of 0.788 and R2 of 0.620 with an F value of 192.891 and a p-value of 0.000, this result proves that technological capability, digital technology is truly needed in achieving Digital Pedagogy 4.0 (Grandeza, 2024). Based on the statistical result it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE. In addition, results from the regression analysis also revealed that the following have a strong influence on the ICT skills and the digital proficiency of teachers' teaching TLE: Professional Views on Computer Technology with a t-value of 12.977 and a p-value of 0.000, Computer Proficiency with a t-value of 10.821 and a p-value of 0.000, and Computer Literacy with a t-value of 9.006 and a p-value of 0.000.

dicators of the ICT skills are combined, they influence the digital proficiency of teachers teaching TLE. Evidently, it was found out that all of the indicators, professional views on com-

Table 4: Significance on the Influence of ICT Skills and the Digital Proficiency of Teachers Teaching TLE

Digital Proficiency	B		t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
Constant	0.761		3.200	0.002	
Professional Views on Computer Technology	0.830	0.767	12.977	0.000	Reject
Computer Literacy	0.568	0.638	9.006	0.000	Reject
Computer Proficiency	0.624	0.706	10.821	0.000	Reject
Summary Statistics					
R	0.788				
R²	0.620				
F	192.891				
	0.000				

puter technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency were significantly related to digital proficiency teachers' teaching TLE. The findings of this study are in conformance with the view of Torrato, Prudente Aguja (2020) revealed that majority of the teachers are somewhat proficient on the technical dimensions of digital literacy namely; hardware and software. For factors influencing technology adoption, results show that they have high perceptions on technology adoption. For technology integration attitude, result suggests positive attitude on technology integration in teaching. These

findings reveal that there is a high level of proficiency and technology integration perception among teachers. Also, in the study conducted by Singhavi Basargekar (2020) concludes that positive perception about ICT as a teaching learning tool positively and significantly impacts teachers' perceived proficiency to use ICT. Moreover, many of the factors such as availability of computer equipment and resources and ICT related digital content contributes perceived proficiency positively. Until then, the findings of the present study are consistent with the results of the previous studies in terms of significant relationship.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This descriptive correlational study aimed to determine the extent of information and communication technology skills of TLE Teachers and the extent of digital proficiency of the teacher's teaching TLE. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of information and communication technology skills of the teachers in terms of professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency. Furthermore, this study also aimed to determine the extent of digital proficiency of the teacher's in terms of Teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, Teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and Factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of information and communication technology skills of the teachers in terms of professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency obtain an overall mean of 4.12 as extensive which means that ICT skills of Teachers is relatively evident. Similarly, the extent of digital proficiency of the teacher's in terms of, teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning obtain an overall mean of 4.04 as extensive. Thus, findings showed that the digital proficiency of teachers is practiced most of the time where teachers are open towards the use of ICT in teaching, not being resistant and feels comfortable in learning new things. Accordingly, there is a significant relationship between teachers' Information Communication Technology (ICT) skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating with an overall r-value of 0.788 and p-value of 0.000 which is lower than the set alpha of 0.05 signifying rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is a strong positive correlation in relationship between teachers' information com-

munication technology (ICT) skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating. Finally, all the domains of information and communication technology skills of the TLE teachers in terms of professional views on computer technology, computer literacy and computer proficiency significantly influence the digital proficiency of the teacher's teaching TLE in terms of teachers' perception of ICT integration in teaching, teachers' effectiveness on the integration of ICT in the classroom and factors in ICT integration in teaching and learning.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the researcher presents the following conclusions: The extent of information and communication technology skills of TLE teachers was extensive. The extent of digital proficiency of TLE teachers was extensive. There was a strong positive correlation in relationship between TLE teachers Information Communication Technology (ICT) skills and digital proficiency technology skills of TLE teachers' classroom observation rating. The ICT skills of the teachers has a significant influence in the digital proficiency of teachers teaching TLE.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were made: The Department of Education should encourage the administrators to develop a fundamental understanding of the importance of using computer technology in the teaching-learning process and suggest better ways of intensive training and equipping teachers with strategies, techniques and approaches. The School Head should conduct and design an intensive training-workshop on the integration of ICT in the classroom and improving the information technology skills of the Teachers. Hence, training might be achieved through the implementation of an effective training program on intensive use of computer technology resources and its practical application in the classroom. The TLE Teach-

ers should update themselves with the various contributions in the use and integration of ICT in the classroom. It may also be useful in identifying the TLE teachers' ICT skills and practices in teaching and its practical application in the classroom. This study will help TLE teachers to identify the level of the utilization of computer technology in the overall teaching-learning process. Thus, it will enable them to identify problems related to the use of computer technology in teaching. Moreover, they will also be aware of their weaknesses and strengths about computer; and consequently, make the necessary adjustments from outdated to updated trainings and seminars. ICT Coordinators should propose a computer literacy program to elevate quality of education of teachers through the use of computer. The students are the recipients of computer literacy program provided to the teachers. Future researchers may use the findings of this study to conduct a similar study which may include the level of actual and evident use of ICT in the classroom and with larger scope to investigate the dimension of the study.

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